

**REFORMING THE INSTITUTIONAL APPROACH
IN THE DRUG LAW ENFORCEMENT
IN MANILA CITY**

A Thesis

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Master in Public Administration

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Bob Aguilar

ABSTRACT

This study is about reforming the institutional approach to drug law enforcement in Manila City. The criminal justice system is essentially defined as a network of agencies and processes that seeks to control and minimize crimes, and impose penalties for committing crimes under the influence of any drug substance. At present, offenders suffered from social injustice within our criminal justice system.

The researcher has gathered data on law enforcement and drug offenders. This is to identify whether the prevailing institutional approach is practical or needs recalibration. The research aims to address the following questions: (1) To identify general approaches used by the law enforcement concerning drug offenders; (2) To know and analyze the percentage rate of drug cases in the City of Manila from 2017 to 2020; (3) To identify and evaluate the implementation of various programs on drug offenders; and (4) To assess community stakeholders' acceptance traits after drug offenders' reformation.

The researcher used mixed method to answer the objectives of this study. This was done through interviews of police officers and drug offenders in selected police stations in the City of Manila. Research questionnaires were also used to gather additional information that really helped in the success of the study. The researcher was able to gather data from 200 participants wherein 100 drug law enforcement and 100 drug offenders.

After analyzing the data, the researcher found out that the City of Manila has an existing criminal justice system. Moreover, there are attempts to enforce the laws on drug offenders with limited success. However, there are still lapses in the present practices of law enforcement, most especially in the reformation of offenders. It is in this context that this study needs to contribute in the improvement of the criminal justice system in the City of Manila.

Keywords: *Criminal Justice, Drug Offenders, Law Enforcement, Social Injustice*

DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to the marginalized sectors in society, policy makers and law enforcement agencies. The researcher hopes that this study will serve as a guide and teach integrity, trust and love of country. Criminal justice plays a vital role in society. It is therefore imperative to treat people equally and with dignity regardless of social status.

DECLARATION OF CONFIDENTIALITY

I hereby acknowledge, by my signature below, that I understand that all of the information and data I have acknowledged and accessed in the course of the research project are confidential and will be used by the University of the East for ethical review and monitoring. This information shall not be disclosed to anyone under any circumstance, except to the extent necessary to fulfill my requirements. I agree to abide by the University Code of Conduct and other professional bodies' codes of conduct and ethical guidelines.

Bob Aguilar

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Chapter 1

RESEARCH PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

This chapter introduces the subject of the study, provides the outline, and reforms the institutional approach to drug law enforcement in the City of Manila. A schematic diagram summarizes the significant variables and presents the hypothesized relationships of the said major variables. The coverage of the study and its limitations are also included in this chapter.

Background of the Study

The criminal justice system in the Philippines has experienced radical changes throughout the nation's history. The current setup is influenced mainly by the system established during the American colonization. The culture of the people affects how the criminal justice system works in the country. The conviction from one's perspective towards the judicial process is a manifestation that can be used to identify whether the law enforcement is adequate or needs to be done to reform drug offenders. Justice is for rendering what is due to a person. It also refers to the peace, order, and well-being of society threatened or disrupted when a crime is committed.

Magtaan (2016) defined the law as a rule of just conduct and made obligatory by legitimate authority for the general welfare and benefit of the people. A law must be just or equal. It means no one is above the law and should apply to everyone. In any law, punishment is permanently attached to deter or control behavior. Laws and punishment must not be feared. Instead, it should be followed for everybody's

protection. Those who are afraid of the law are only those who violate the law. People should realize that they should know the punishment for violating the law.

The design flow of the law enforcement in the Philippine criminal justice system mandates a specific agency responsible for enforcing laws, maintaining public order, and managing public safety. As a result, drug-related crimes are designated to the Philippine Drug Enforcement Authority (PDEA) and Philippine National Police (PNP). The primary purpose of this design is to ensure the balance and coordination of law enforcement operations.

According to the PNP, the current police population ratio is 1:572, while the national standard is 1:500. In the City of Manila, the current ratio is 1:2000. Based on this data, a police officer must serve four times higher than the national standard (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2022). There are fifteen (15) police stations, including the Manila Police District as the central police office in the city. There are 7,000 police officers deployed. Each station has less than 300 police officers (Senate No. 231, 2019).

In 2020, the drug-related cases in the Philippines declined by more than 50%, from four (4) million in 2016 to 1.67 million in 2019, three years after President Rodrigo Duterte's crackdown on drug use. According to the Dangerous Drug Board (DDB), there is an estimated 2.05% prevalence rate as of 2020, significantly lower than in 2018, with regards to the global estimated of 5.3% as the World Drug Report of 2020 published (Xinhua, 2020).

The Dangerous Drug Board under the executive office reported that in 2016, new admission in the rehabilitation centers related to drugs reached 77.12%, and most of them were male. Meanwhile, the re-admission marked a total of 18.52%. During the drug war, as implemented by President Duterte, 2019 records showed that rehabilitation admission was significantly increased by 97.93%, while the re-admission in 2019 decreased to 0.42%. This was extremely positive on the administration side (DDB, 2016).

Behind this success against the war on drugs of the Duterte administration, the United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights estimated the number of deaths with 8,663 cases related to drug operations from July 2016 to June 2020. This was far different from the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) reports, which had only 6,201 deaths from July 2016 to September 2021 (U.N., 2020).

On the other hand, new initiatives to reform the approach are used by the institution to play a vital role, resulting in a mindset of cooperation and collaboration in the programs. It helps resolve or ease the problem that society is currently experiencing through the different circumstances. Law enforcement's lawful approach to the victims or offenders might significantly influence the country's current trend of deliverance practices.

Historically, the leadership of law enforcement in the country transformed into a different approach to cleansing the department and identifying corrupt officials and employees involved in illegal activities. All teams were reshuffled and re-assigned in different localities. The strategic planning in the organization was the directive of the

current administration as head of state and chief of law enforcement in the country. However, the corrupt practices in the department were established over a long period, and the involvement of all officials and employees was also transformed bureaucratically. This was the reason behind implementing these new initiatives and directions.

The researcher aims to reform and create an in-depth analysis of the justice system to understand better the institutional approach to drug law enforcement in Manila city. One can expect that at the end of this analysis, a set of reviews about the criminal justice system will be identified and can be utilized in formulating the remedies to meet the needs of the people and solve the problems confronting the country's criminal justice system.

The study focuses on the institutional approach of drug law enforcement in the criminal justice system in the city of Manila, which necessitates a thorough analysis as it covers one of the fundamental institutions in society. Each citizen is vulnerable to becoming a victim of a disintegrated criminal justice system and consequently finds himself caught in a system supported by a weak foundation of the judicial process and state foundation.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The 1987 Philippine Constitution serves as the fundamental and domestic law that guarantees the right of every person to life, liberty, or even the right to due process, nor the right to have equal protection of the law. From this viewpoint, the government is strictly mandated to implement all fundamental rights of every person. Added to this is the duty of the state to initiate a reform to integrate the prevailing system of justice in the country for the general public's interest.

Based on the country's prevailing theories of Criminal Justice, criminal law begins with criminalization. The action of any person makes the person liable for the commission of the crime, and the criminal system in the country confers a set of investigations to gather evidence of the crime committed. The stop and search carry out the aspect of exercising law enforcement to generate evidence for the interest of the state and the public.

The theory of justice attempted to develop a nonutilitarian justification of a democratic political order characterized by fairness, equality, and individual rights. The primary purpose is to revive the social contract in which the rational groups or individuals are rendered ignorant of all social and economic facts. The general principles should govern the political institutions under which they live (R.A Dahl, 2020).

This theory is a very instrumental guide in achieving a fair justice system. In Manila, most drug offenders are in the marginalized sector and, under this theory, provide equality and promote individual rights regardless of their social status. The

poor can easily access government programs, and special treatment will be set aside. Law enforcers will implement the can without any discretion, and the court's judgment will be more rational than the current system in presenting the burden of proof.

The American philosopher John Rawls argued that the reason for veil ignorance is the unanimous rejection of the practical principles such as political institutions should maximize the happiness of the most significant number. Given the assumptions about human motivation, Rawls holds that some inequality practices prevail in which those who are least well-off are better off than they would be under an equal society (R.A Dahl, 2020).

While it is true that utilitarian principles should be a primary consideration in implementing the law, the number of drug offenders in Manila shows that human motivation to survive is the main reason why offenders are involved in any illegal drug activities. The mandate of law enforcement to serve and protect the citizenry is challenging due to the involvement of some high-profile personalities.

Moral theory, theory systematize and codify the judgments of conduct or behavior. It provides accountability to all, including public servants. The principle is for the decision-making, particularly in cases of morally relevant concepts, including the ethical aspect (J.L Nolen, 2020 D.B Resnik, 2018).

The German philosopher Immanuel Kant emphasized the importance of dignity, autonomy, and goodwill. This is why Timmons 2002 argued that moral theories differ from scientific ones. It is because the observation, tests, or experiment

cannot perform a similar types of procedures to identify the moral aspect (D.B Resnik 2018).

Kant's moral theory is relevant in the investigation process under the criminal justice system, in which the frontline in the implementation and enforcement are the police officers in the city. The current chain of custody is manipulative, and the offenders can be subject to more cases if they will question the process unless a lawyer properly represents the offender. However, most drug offenders in the city are of the marginalized status.

Another theory is a reformatory theory in which the method of individualism of the offenders is considered. According to this theory, the punishment must consider the factors. Among other things, the demographic profile of the offenders is essential, like age, character, and nature of the crime committed (A. Gupta, 2021).

Mahatma Gandhi stated that an eye for an eye would make the whole world blind. This theory of reformatory Indian philosophy aims to reform the penal system and ensures that offenders' relationship remains intact. Gandhi also highlighted that securing the employment of offenders after the reformation is very important for returning to society as reformed offenders (A. Gupta, 2021).

This reformatory theory provides a substantive process contributing to the criminal justice system's goal of recalibrating its drug law enforcement approaches. This study reinforces the planning and development of concrete reforms to lessen the general approaches used by the agencies. It urges the reformation of drug offenders through humanistic methods and principles during incarceration.

The theories mentioned above are closely interrelated in the justice system considered in the reformatory objective for the drug offenders in terms of economic, emotional, and developmental aspects. In the theory of justice, all offenders should be treated the same regardless of social status. And the moral theory is instrumental to the system of implementation that law enforcers should act on the case based on evidence and not on their discretions. In contrast, the reformatory theory is needed to reform the offenders and get them back into society.

Although this research recognizes the importance of the role of all pillars in the criminal justice system, the main focus of the study is only on law enforcement as one of the pillars. It is indeed true that each of these five pillars is significantly interrelated to each other in performing an analysis of law enforcement as a government approach.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The criminal justice system is the conceptual framework used to discuss the relation of its variable in this study. Drug law enforcement, which is the front liner to enforce the law used as respondents to measure its awareness, procedural and substantive process of their mandate. The enforcement outcome proposed viable plan using the shared framework in achieving its goal. At the same time, community acceptance measures the total recovery of the offenders. Their family, peers, and the job opportunity in the City of Manila will improve the approaches to save the life of the drug offenders.

Figure 1
Conceptual Framework

The above figure shows that the researcher used the criminal justice system as the main framework to evaluate the institutional approach of drug law enforcement in the City of Manila. The profile of the drug offenders is essentially needed to assess

their background and the main reason for involvement. From this, the educational attainment and social and marital status of the drug offenders were considered for the researcher to find answers,

The economic condition of the drug offenders squeezed them to do such illegal acts. It is expected that their motivations to survive for their daily needs force them not to consider whether they are doing right or wrong. And the emotional status of every offender significantly influences their needs to survive. Food for their family or their motivation to provide a decent life for their children drives them into illegal drug activity.

The drug law enforcement PNP and PDEA are mandated to enforce the law in the City of Manila. The researcher identified selected officers under PNP and DPEA as the respondents. The researcher provided the questionnaire to measure their awareness of the prevailing approaches. The demographics of the drug law enforcement are needed to assess some technicalities in enforcing the law. While the face-to-face interview is needed to evaluate their authentic expression and knowledge and if there is any discrepancy in their answers.

The drug enforcement outcome will be able to manifest if the institutional approaches were practical or not. A proposed plan to improve the institutional approach for drug offenders is pivotal in achieving the institutional goal. It is also essential to identify what shared framework is best for all agencies with a mandate to save its citizenry from drug problems.

In addition, the community acceptance of reformed offenders is vital. Most importantly, to their family, peers, and if there is employment opportunity after their reformation. From this view, the drug offenders' developmental aspect will sustain them to change.

Further, the conceptual framework shows the flow of the institutional approach in saving these drug offenders in the community. The Criminal Justice System is the main framework of the institution of this country, a system created under the constitutional mandate.

The participation of stakeholders with the collaboration of the system pillars will quantify the program's success for the drug offenders' reformation in the community. The program's effects support the system's approaches, and stakeholders set to the drug offenders to provide new life and hope for change. However, if the approaches of these essential elements are a failure, it will always go back to the justice system and its weak points to cause failure. Since the justice system is created to restore and reformate these offenders' lives, the institutional system should uphold the sworn duties and responsibility to the country and society. If the justice system is transparent, the multi-stakeholders will follow and support their collaborative effort in achieving one goal for society.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the condition of the drug offenders, in terms of:
 - a. Economic Status
 - b. Emotional Condition
2. What are the general approaches used by law enforcement concerning drug offenders?
3. What is the percentage rate of drug cases in the city of Manila from 2017 up to 2020?
4. What is the extent of the agency's implementation of its various programs in dealing with drug offenders?
5. What are the acceptance traits of stakeholders in the community after the reformation of drug offenders?

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

An independent T-test was conducted to determine if a significant mean difference exists between the drug law enforcement, such as PDEA and the PNP concerning the institutional enforcement of the law in the criminal justice system, as guided by these hypotheses:

Ho: There is no significant difference between drug law enforcement such as PDEA and the PNP concerning the institutional enforcement of the law in the criminal justice system.

Ha: There is a significant difference between drug law enforcement such as PDEA and the PNP concerning the institutional approach implemented to reform drug offenders.

SCOPE AND DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study focuses on drug law enforcement in the city of Manila. The respondents comprised 50 PDEA, 50 PNP members, and 100 drug suspects. With 200 research participants, the researcher conducted the study in the inclusive years of 2017 until this study's drug law enforcement was categorized according to their years of service, educational background, and position in the agency. At the same time, the drug offenders are classified according to their demographic crimes committed.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study on the criminal justice system can serve as a basis to improve the policy process in Manila due to malpractices by officers, specifically the people belonging to the drug law enforcement.

Correctional Institutions

They must be serviceable in reforming offenders as the criminal justice system mandates.

Community

Provide awareness about a criminal justice system to increase community acceptance of drug offenders.

Drug Offenders

For them to know all government agencies and programs available for the drug offenders.

Policymakers

Help in crafting the policies for the improvement of the system to ensure research-based procedures.

Law Enforcers

To guide them in enforcing the law and caution to the procedural and subjective process that the justice system requires.

Stakeholders

To encourage support of community programs towards total reformation of offenders.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF TERMS

Community. It refers to institutions, government, non-government agencies, and people's organizations that provide care and assistance to the victims or offended party during and after the onset of a victims' rights case.

Correctional Institutions. It refers to institutions mandated to administer correctional and rehabilitation programs for the offenders. These programs develop the offenders' or convicts' abilities and potentials and facilitate their re-integration into the community and everyday family life.

Courts. It refers to the Metropolitan Trial Courts and Regional Trial Courts designated to handle and try the case and issue judgment after trial.

Criminal Justice System. It refers to the series of government agencies and institutions. The primary goal is for the rehabilitation of offenders, to prevent other crimes, and for moral support for victims.

Drug Law Enforcement. It refers to the sub-unit of the law enforcement agency like the PDEA and Drug Division in PNP, which is mandated to enforce and solve drug criminality in the country.

Institutional Approach. It refers to the government programs mandated and created under the rule of law to reconfigure all drug offenders in the country.

Irregularities. It refers to the state or quality of being improper or dishonest in the job.

Law Enforcement. It refers to government agencies charged with the enforcement of penal laws. It is primarily responsible for investigating whether an offense has been committed and, where needed, the apprehension of alleged offenders for further investigation of the Prosecution Service.

Prosecution Service. It refers to the National Prosecution Service (NPS), mandated to investigate and prosecute penal violations. It collates, evaluates evidence in the preliminary inquest investigation, and dismisses or files the case in court as indicated.

Reformation. It refers to the act or process of improving something or someone by removing or correcting faults and problems.

Chapter 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES AND SYNTHESIS

The following related literature and studies are selected to guide the author in understanding the institutional approach of drug law enforcement in the City of Manila. The literature and studies are grouped as follows: Criminal Justice System, System Institutional Problem, Pillars of Criminal Justice System, Institutional Approach, and Government Support.

Criminal Justice System

Cano (2017) explains the concept of the criminal justice system in the Philippines. According to her, these are established institutions to maintain peace and order and are responsible for preventing crimes, enforcing laws, apprehension, and prosecuting those who violate the law. When the courts of law find them guilty of committing crimes, they shall be confined, rehabilitated, and reintegrated into the community to become law-abiding citizens.

Government agencies should have incorporated themselves to establish an effective Criminal Justice System. The Court is the cornerstone of the system, which determines whether the person charged for a criminal offense is guilty or not. When the Courts of Law find an individual guilty of violating the law, a sentence shall be imposed upon him, not for the person to change his attitude, but as a penalty. When the person is proven guilty beyond a reasonable doubt, he must be placed in confinement for his protection and the community's welfare. He is considered a prisoner while serving his sentence imposed by the court for transgressing the law.

Nelid (2017) explores the susceptibility of politics to influence the criminal justice system at every level. Since the law is mandated by politicians, politics influences all aspects of the law and criminal justice system to a large degree. And since politicians are influenced by all factors, including the media, their constituents, donors, business, and lobbyists, the criminal justice system is also influenced by all those factors.

The decision-makers in the criminal justice system, particularly the judges, are publically appointed, so politics comes into play. Although it is the judges' job to be impartial, the truth is that political motivations can influence their ability to make impartial decisions. So, since the criminal justice system is run by politicians or appointees that are either voted for or assigned by politicians, politics dramatically influences how the law is applied.

In an article published in DAWN (2015) entitled flawed justice system, criminal justice reform is, unfortunately, a subject that does not rank very highly on the rulers' list of priorities. Whether the trial of violent criminals or terrorists, investigation agencies and courts fail to probe cases scientifically and deliver verdicts based on incontrovertible evidence. The result is apparent in the low conviction rates, and general lawlessness that prevails in society. Criminals and militants are aware that there are good chances that they can get away with their crimes.

The article of Dawn also claims that faulty investigations and a lack of witness protection are to blame for the low conviction rate. Moreover, lack of coordination

between investigation agencies and prosecutors and a heavy backlog of cases are some factors standing in the way of justice delivery.

Cruz (2014) stated that the Philippines holds the Guinness World Record for having the slowest pace in running the judicial system. He emphasized the two mass killings in the Philippines: The Maguindanao massacre, where 58 poor souls, including 32 media workers, were murdered, and the Ozone Disco Club fire in Quezon City that claimed the lives of 162 people, most of them young men and women celebrating their graduation. In the Ozone Disco fire, the trial of those responsible for the tragedy took almost 19 years, much longer than the sentences imposed on them by the court.

Cruz (2014) also highlighted why this occurred in the justice system. First, he described it as "clogged court dockets," with too many cases being tried by too few courts and judges. This gets worse every year. As new cases pile up, fewer and fewer cases get to be decided by the courts. Another is the dilatory tactics by the defense and the lackadaisical attitude of the judges. A motion for postponement is almost always granted by the judges who feel no urgency to finish a case quickly. Most judges conduct trials for only half a day.

Reiman and Leighton (2016) contend that the criminal justice system is biased against the poor from beginning to end. The authors argue that even before the arrest, trial, and sentencing process, the system is biased against the poor in what it chooses to treat as a crime. The dangerous acts of the well-off are rarely treated as crimes, compared to the crimes committed by the poor, which are severely treated. Not only does the criminal justice system fail to protect against the harmful acts of well-off

people, but it also fails to remedy the causes of crime, such as poverty. This results in many poor criminals in prisons and the media.

Reiman and Leighton (2016) also contend that the idea of crime as a work of the poor serves the interests of the rich and powerful while conveying a misleading notion that the real threat to Americans comes from the bottom of society rather than the top. Doob (2014) stated the same observation from the research findings of the criminological highlights that those with the slightest knowledge about the criminal justice system are the least confident in its operation.

System Institutional Problem

Conde (2016) cited numerous sources of injustice; corrupt and incompetent investigators and prosecutors, a judicial and court system clogged with too many cases, and too few judges to try them. The institutional pathologies result in unjust and prolonged detention. Many detainees have been in jail longer than the maximum sentence for the offense with which they were charged, with some people spending as long as 14 years in detention before being convicted or released by the courts. The injustice of lengthy detention is compounded by the horrific conditions of the jail facilities.

The detention centers in the Philippines fail to meet the minimum United Nations standards for such facilities, including inadequate food, poor nutrition, and unsanitary conditions. Torture and other forms of ill-treatment are also common. Because most of those who run afoul of the law are poor, posting bail is often not an

option. And even if they can afford bail, the majority of detainees in most of these jails face drug charges that are nonbailable.

Abadines (2017) showed staggering statistics highlighting one of the most critical problems in the justice system in the Philippines, not enough courts to meet society's demands. He quoted Chief Justice Maria Lourdes Sereno to further justify this disparity in the justice system, "In the Philippines, there are only 2,000 courts nationwide that serve a population of a hundred million. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority, a judge would have an insane average annual workload of 644 cases which yielded to the massive issue of the length it takes for cases to be decided.

A great example is the case of former president Gloria Macapagal Arroyo and former Makati mayor Elena Binay, wherein the Sandiganbayan has dismissed the cases due to the delays which led to the acquittal of corrupt public officials. Hence, the low conviction rates in the Sandiganbayan somehow manifest that the country's legal system failed in its meaning and objectives.

Aileru (2016) identified the defects of the criminal justice system in Nigeria, one of which is the frequent delays that characterize criminal trials. The delays are mostly part of how lawyers often explore the loopholes in the law to frustrate trials, usually by filing frivolous applications and objections in court. The average time a criminal trial proceeding takes before the act's enactment is four to six years. Also, how much longer a trial can be delayed depends on the caliber of the lawyers involved, the status of the accused person, and the nature of the offense charged.

According to Aileru, the most common delay tactic is raising preliminary objections by challenging the trial court's jurisdiction or the validity of the charge based on perceived defects (sometimes imaginary and illusory). The trial court will be forced to rule on the objection one way or the other. Upon the trial court's ruling, an appeal will quickly be filed at the Court of Appeal.

Another is that depending on how competent the lawyer is. This may take another two years. Meanwhile, a stay of execution would have been granted, preventing the trial court from continuing the original proceedings. After the Court of Appeal judgment on the objection, a subsequent appeal may be lodged at the Supreme Court, which may take another two years before it is heard. While this was happening, the accused would have been granted bail.

Gana (2015) highlighted the difficulties of the prosecutorial part of the government in case building. Criminal prosecutions have always been tough balancing acts for the state. While the state, through its representatives, is mandated to ensure that those who have transgressed societal norms are brought to trial and be made to suffer to the fullest extent of the law. It is also essential to ensure that the innocent must not be unduly burdened by criminal prosecution. Bearing this in mind, public prosecutors have a heavy burden to ensure that only the guilty are prosecuted and sentenced.

However, Gana stated that there are discrepancies in presenting evidence during the trial because of the procedure that the public prosecutor merely relies on the evidence presented by the private offended, and the pieces of evidence presented to

them are the same evidence that they will use to prosecute the accused during the trial. This becomes problematic considering the different variables that must be considered.

The probable cause should be the standard coupled with the fact that the public prosecutor merely receives evidence from different parties leads to congested criminal dockets of the courts and overworked prosecutors. Because of this, the public prosecutor fails to present proof beyond a reasonable doubt, the quantum of proof sufficient to produce a moral certainty that would convince and satisfy the conscience of those who act in judgment.

Furthermore, because the evidence presented during the trial was sourced by either the private offender or the police, the public prosecutor must return to them to fill in the gaps in the evidence to obtain a verdict. Further, as courts become beleaguered by cases that should not have reached the courts, these cases consume a lot of court time, thereby prolonging the trial of all cases. This causes the unnecessarily prolonged detention of prisoners.

Lopez (2009) outlined several factors that could negatively affect the building of cases for the less privileged. These factors can be classified into those about the pauper litigants and the public attorneys. In the case of the poor litigants, the factors identified are their submissive attitude, inability to communicate with their lawyers because of *hiya*, lack of education and knowledge of the law, and lack of family support. Their inability to communicate with their lawyers and lack of knowledge of the law prevent the poor from sharing their interpretation of the case with their lawyers and probably demanding better service from their counsel.

In the case of public attorneys, the overwhelming number of cases they handle primarily causes constraints in case building. Because of their workload, public attorneys do not have time to rigorously interview the litigants and witnesses who will provide the necessary facts for the case. The inability of the public attorneys to rigorously interview the poor litigants' results in the formers' failure to fully take into account the context of their client's case. In marshaling evidence to build a robust theory of the case, there is a need to weigh the symbolic representation to arrive at a unity of meaning that would bolster the construction of the case.

Also, the public attorneys do not have investigators who will help them gather evidence and legal researchers who will provide them with information necessary for building the case theory. In addition, the PAO does not have a complete library; hence, critical legal materials are not easily accessible to public attorneys. PAO lawyers also cannot quickly secure their clients' transcripts of stenographic notes, thereby further limiting the time they are supposed to devote to studying their cases.

Varona (2010) discovered in his research in the Philippine National Police institution that low pay frequently leads to other forms of corruption, such as the tendency for police to extort and collect bribes. Bribery and extortion, along with patronage politics, are highly prevalent in the Philippines' Criminal Justice System. In the Philippine National Police, part of that system, internal corruption is particularly prevalent in the service's recruitment and logistics procurement mechanisms and the allocation of funds and resources.

Pillars of the Criminal Justice System

Brown (2015) questions the police force in the Philippines in his article entitled "Bad Apples," stating that incidents of crime and violence involving policemen are usually treated as individual acts of misbehavior and are attributed to the idea that there are a few "bad apples" in every barrel. "Scalawags" and "erring policemen" are commonly used to describe cops who violated the law. These events are commonplace and indicate a much deeper problem, as well as a complete refusal of the senior leadership to treat the situation with the seriousness it deserves.

Brown (2015) cited some incidents where the wrongdoings of the cops are manifested, such as standard reports about a group of cops who abduct a person, usually under the pretense of making an arrest. The poor guy is often taken to the police station and then carted off to a private residence, where he is either robbed or held for ransom. In other cases, he may be held at the police station and forced to pay the officers so they won't file a separate charge against him.

According to Brown, this happens because supervisors are not supervising. Procedures already exist to prevent this kind of activity, but they are not being followed, and they are not being enforced. Because in the informal world of Philippine police work, individual cops are allowed to operate so independently that supervisors rarely bother to question their activities. Brown stated that Supervisors have the power to eliminate this problem. If station commanders and shift supervisors require proper documentation and monitor their people's activities, most criminal behavior by police officers would simply be impossible.

Marcello (2017) cited the Commission on Audit in her article that Philippine jails are already overpopulated by 511 percent, as the number of inmates ballooned to 126,946 as of the end of 2016, which exceeded the total ideal jail capacity of 20,746 inmates. The audit body said this overcrowding in the country's district jails, city jails, municipal jails, extension jails, and female dormitories violates BJMP's own "Manual on Habitat, Water, Sanitation and Kitchen in Jails" as well as the United Nations' "Minimum Standard Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners."

Asian Legal Resource Centre and Asian Human Rights Commission (2007) reveal a pattern of extreme cruelty and state complicity. Filipinos are being threatened, tortured, abducted, killed, and destroyed with brutality that no civilized state would permit. This cruel behavior is permitted and encouraged because the country's institutions for criminal justice are so barbaric that together they bear no resemblance to any modern system of justice. Most in the Filipino elite will find such remarks offensive.

In the Philippines, law-enforcement agencies are utterly corrupt and evil in their dealings with the public. If rights on paper are ever to be given life there, the top priority must be to transform the country's errant and self-serving policing system into one that will serve the people. Public prosecutors are closely associated with the role of the police. Prosecutors are integral in ensuring that criminal justice works with integrity and speed. Where policing and prosecution are flawed.

Institutional Approach

Estabillo A. (2021) wrote in the Philippine News Agency about the reformed livelihood aid for drug offenders, which has allotted a budget for those who have graduated from an innovative reformation program in General Santos City. The city also offered assistance with value formation, bookkeeping, essential business management, and skill training. Beneficiaries are subject to monitoring by the PSWDO – Provincial Social Welfare Development Office for six months after the release of the grants. In addition, beneficiaries need to undergo information and education sessions on the illegal drug campaign and the provisions of Republic Act 9165 or the Comprehensive Dangerous Drug Act of 2002.

Michaelson (2015) presented the case of Michael Brown, who was killed by a police officer in Ferguson, Missouri. Police misconduct across the nation has been scrutinized and debated. Police misconduct is just one piece of a flawed justice system. In the Michael Brown case, the fact that the police officer who killed Brown was never indicted caused national outrage, but the prosecutor responsible for that decision faced few repercussions and ran for reelection unopposed.

Michaelson stated that misconduct has few repercussions because prosecutors are given immunity. And the entire system has a racial bias problem: ninety-five percent of prosecutors across the country are white, yet forty percent of the incarcerated population is black. This research done by Michaelson reflected that the judicial system throughout the world is tainted with partiality, and fairness is not manifested.

Government Support

Caliwan et al. (2010) found out that having a PAO lawyer is a bad thing to have in the state of our justice system. As the research suggests, they do not know/the power complex one needs so that a litigant can create a good tactic for one's case. Their research has also shown, through secondary data analysis and court observations, that status symbols or power dynamics have primarily played a powerful force because by including them in the litigation process, the litigant (inmate) is greatly favored and given leniency. Their research has presented different and varied observations concerning the symbolic relation in court litigation. The silent participation of the inmate/litigants shows that only those recognized by society as knowing/power complex are given a chance to speak their minds.

In the study conducted by Mejia, C., Atienza, B., Alquisada, P., Villaluz, A., Viniegra, C., Bedural, V.F. (2010) entitled "Assessment of the Capacity of Pillars of the Philippine Criminal Justice System," the authors stated that the common problem plaguing the pillars of the CJS is the lack of funding to pursue their programs. For the prosecution pillar, the number of cases handled by the lawyers affects their performance. The more cases a lawyer handles, the less attention is given to individual cases. This affects the prosecution of the cases and the speedy disposition of cases. It affects the congestion of court dockets and jails.

According to the authors, "access to justice is undermined if the evidence is not gathered or properly preserved to support a case, if prosecution is delayed, and if legal assistance to poor litigants is not available or the quality of legal services is not satisfactory to support the requirements of the concerned party. Furthermore, success

is also limited by lack of awareness by poor litigants of the services available to them, distant geographical proximity, unavailability of public attorneys and prosecutors, and the inability of the DOJ to defray the cost of these services considering severe funding limitations. At the heart of the Criminal Justice System is the court's pillar.

The support of the correctional institution for the reformation and rehabilitation of the offenders has been neglected. The concerned institutions insist that the government should invest in the modernization of the correctional system because if their programs are not practical due to a lack of governmental support, then recidivism will possibly occur. Crime accidents become a cycle if the reformation and rehabilitation programs are ineffective. Moreover, institutions are concerned with the prevailing negative perception toward their clients. Thus, there is a need to create awareness of these agencies' rehabilitation and reformation programs. This will mainly be beneficial in community-based corrections.

RESEARCH SYNTHESIS

Altogether, the literature and studies presented earlier created a scenario where the five pillars of the criminal justice system seem ineffective. This necessitates a prompt revisiting by the country's policymakers and demands a need for improvement of the institutional approach of the state for the offenders. Cruz stated in his article that the Philippines is in the Guinness World Record for the slowest judicial system as he showed the slow wheels of justice that manifest in almost all cases filed in court. This is attributed to the system problem of the criminal justice system in the Philippines.

Some authors cited numerous causes of these defects in our justice system; Conde stated in his article that corrupt and incompetent investigators and prosecutors, a judicial and court system clogged with too many cases, and too few judges to try them are some of the sources of the injustice in the justice system. The five pillars have been highlighted, and, in each pillar, the afflictions are manifested. Bribery and extortion are standard practices of law enforcers in the law enforcement pillar, and proper procedure is not followed, resulting in corruption and violations of the people's fundamental rights as stipulated in the constitution.

This is highly prevalent in the Philippine criminal justice system. Moreover, laws are not adequately enforced and are attributed to the misconduct of police officers, thereby contributing to the flawed justice system. The slow justice system in the Philippines is attributed to the defense's dilatory tactics, the judges' lax attitude, and too many cases being tried by too few courts and judges, according to the courts' pillar. These make the Philippines the Southeast Asian country with the highest

number of pretrial and remand detainees and the second-highest in all of Asia. Only those recognized by society as knowing/power complex are allowed to speak their minds in the prosecution pillar.

Justice is only for those who can afford it; this has been a common notion. Power dynamics can be seen at every turn in the justice system, from how long or short your trial can be determined by how good your lawyers are and how quickly you can pay for your speedy trial. The justice system appears to have a built-in bias favoring people from wealthy backgrounds, and the poor cannot have access to the justice system because they can't afford it. In the pillar, Correctional, far too many people in the Philippines are detained for long periods without seeing a judge or whose infrequent court appearances last years.

Chapter 3

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design and methodology of the study. It includes procedures for gathering data as well as research instruments. It also discusses the validation process and provides a detailed explanation, analysis, and data collection.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study used a mixed-method approach. The quantitative method was used to gather data using a self-formulated questionnaire to evaluate the demographic profile of the respondents and the percentage rate of drug cases in the City of Manila. At the same time, the qualitative method is used to assess the general approaches of drug law enforcement and its implementation of various programs. It also determines the community's acceptance of the drug offenders.

SOURCES OF DATA

The researcher focused on drug law enforcement in the Philippine justice system towards reformation and integration into society in the city of Manila. Involved agencies such as LGU of Manila, DILG, PDEA, Manila Police District, and target drug offenders were utilized for the research to get the results. The designated data were gathered from community members, law enforcement, and drug offenders.

RESPONDENTS OF THE STUDY

The researcher considered the drug law enforcement in the criminal justice system, which is the Philippine National Police, under Manila District with 50 participants, and the Philippine Drug Enforcement Authority with 50 participants, for the total of 100 participants retrieved/gathered in the drug law enforcement. The researcher also gathered data from the drug offenders in the city of Manila with 100 participants, consequently producing a total of 200 respondents for this study.

RESEARCH LOCALE

The study was conducted in the City of Manila under the drug law enforcement department, the Philippine National Police (PNP) in Manila, and the Philippine Drug Enforcement Authority (PDEA). The study considered the data from 2017 - 2020.

SAMPLING DESIGN

The researcher used purposive random sampling. Initially, the researcher identified several police stations in the city of Manila with numerically high cases of drug offenders. Then, from therein, the researcher proceeded in the administration of the survey and the interview with selected officers of the PDEA and PNP and drug offenders as well.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The researcher used a mixed-method approach and documents provided by the government agencies. For drug law enforcement, a self-formulated questionnaire is composed of three parts: first, the demographic profile of the respondents; second, the general approaches in the criminal justice system; and lastly, the respondents' awareness of procedural and substantive processes.

For drug offenders, the researcher also used a self-formulated questionnaire composed of the three parts: first, respondents' demographics; second, their crimes committed; and lastly, the reason for involvement.

DATA GATHERING PROCEDURE

The following are the steps followed by the researcher:

- The researcher visited government agencies such as PDEA, MPD, DILG, and LGU of Manila for the data gathering (*personally submitted communication letter to the government agencies*).
- The researcher obtained a permit to conduct research studies, gather data, and undergo interviews with the concerned government agencies such as LGU of Manila, DILG, MPD, and PDEA.
- The researcher conducted actual interviews, and the data gathered were compared to the reports reflected on the system of the justice system.
- The researcher mainly used the government reports to provide tables for analysis.
- The researcher compared the gathered data records if there was a significant change in the justice system with the government approach.
- The researcher then compiled all the information yielded throughout the research.
- The researcher followed a mixed-method approach which was the use of cluster and purposive sampling techniques.
- The researcher analyzed and interpreted the data.
- The researcher wrote a summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

VALIDATION PROCESS

Questionnaire was validated by a legal expert who practiced and taught in the field of criminal law for an extended period. To ensure the rights of the drug offenders in the criminal system, the researcher asked a former Attorney II in Public Attorney's Office (PAO) and currently a private legal practitioner in his private Law Firm to do the validation process. The researcher also seeks assistance from a Social Science Professor in the University of Perpetual Help System - Jonelta under the Department of Senior High School and College of Arts and Sciences to validate the table and qualitative data to ensure the interpretation of these data is indeed correct.

Corollary, all data gathered (*qualitative and quantitative*) was consulted with the statistician expert and currently connected in the University of the East, Manila, a Department Head and teaching in the different colleges such as Arts and Sciences, Mathematics, Basic Education Department, and, a faculty member in the Graduate School.

STATISTICAL TREATMENT

The researcher used Excel office tools, and all the data were encoded for analysis to get the standard deviation, mean, and percentage. The following formula was considered in this research:

For Percentage:

$$P = \frac{x}{y} \cdot 100\%$$

where:

P = the percentage

x is the number of respondents who answered

y is the total respondents of the subject research.

For Mean:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{n}$$

where:

\bar{X} = Mean

X = values observed

n = number of values observed

Standard Deviation:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (X - \bar{X})^2}{n - 1}}$$

where:

s = standard deviation

X = observed values

\bar{X} = mean

N = number of observed values

Chapter 4
PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS,
AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the findings of the study. The gathered data were analyzed using the mixed-method approach to examine the study's variables. It includes a discussion of the relationship of data. It shows the correlation between the findings and related literature of the study.

The data gathered comprised the drug enforcement operation in the City of Manila from 2017 to 2020. Drug-related cases include operations conducted, cases filed in court, and arrests of classified pushers and users. For purposes of clarity and organization, the researcher showed the following tables to show the answers to the following specific research questions:

*Research Question 1: What is the condition of the drug offenders
 In terms of economic and emotional?*

The table below shows the demographics of drug offenders in Manila from 2017 to 2020.

Table 1
Drug Offenders Demographics in Manila, 2017-2020

Profile	Dominant	(N)	Percentage	Mean	SD
Gender	Male	100	61%	1.55	0.08
Marital Status	Married	100	46%	2.09	0.11
Emotional	Depressed	100	61%	1.55	0.08
Economic Status	Blue Collar	100	43%	4.96	0.33
Age Range	26-30yrs old	100	42%	4.27	0.12

Source: Data from 100 Identified Drug Offenders in the City of Manila

Table 1 shows that most drug offenders in Manila were male, aged 26 to 30, married, and in the blue-collar sector. From the data above, it is crucial to consider that these offenders were economically or financially unstable to enter any drug-related activities. Members of the families relied on the father of the house, who are generally the provider of all basic needs to survive the basic day-to-day needs. From this, the emotional status of the offenders is also affected by worrying about tomorrow. They are also under depression due to family and personal conflict.

Generally, the researcher was able to gather data from 100 drug offenders in Manila. From this, the offenders' job classification with percentage responses are as follows (1) White Collar (Working Professionals), 0%; (2) Blue Collar (Middle Workers/Laborer), 43%; (3) Pink Collar (Beauty care and healthcare), 5%; (4) Gold Collar (Business Owners), 15%; (5) Grey Collar (Retired but still working), 0%; (6) Orange Collar (Mining and Construction workers), 0%; (7) Black Collar (Artists and Producers), 0%; (8) Red Collar (Government officers/Employee), 0%; and (9) No Collar (Jobless/Unemployed), 35%.

Lopez (2009) outlined several factors that could negatively affect the offenders' emotional and economic well-being. In the case of the poor litigants, the factors identified are their submissive attitude, inability to communicate with their lawyers because of *hiya*, lack of education and knowledge of the law, and lack of family support. Their inability to communicate with their lawyers and lack of knowledge of the law prevent the poor from sharing their interpretation of the case with their lawyers and probably demanding better service from their counsel.

Research Question 2: What are the prevailing approaches used by law enforcement concerning drug offenders?

Approaches in drug law enforcement are essential to reforming the country's drug offenders. As far as the government is concerned, the overall approach to educating the people in the community is the "Community Seminars." The PDEA conducted several programs and seminars focusing on the young generations to inform them of all possible effects and consequences involving drug use. The Philippine National Police conducted the famous but notorious war against drugs of the government, which is a famous play of words, namely: "toktok," or knock, and "hangyo," or plead, and "TOKHANG" or toktok and hangyo combined, a case of linguistic coinage. "TOKHANG" was implemented as an initial approach, characterized as a severe intimate dialogue with the suspected drug offender, followed by interventions by the drug law enforcement based on the instructions of PDEA or members of the PNP. They are enforcers and receive orders from higher-ups.

The monitoring mechanism consisted of a community initiative providing reports and updates to concerned authorities. The Barangay Anti-Drug Abuse Council or BADAC was mandated to monitor and provide initial reports to any drug-related case and person under monitoring in the respective barangay. All summative reports were strictly required to be submitted to government agencies such as PNP, PDEA, DILG, and MADAC, under the LGU of Manila. Assistance in all forms, financial or otherwise, from stakeholders, educational sectors, and community sectors was vital in reforming all drug offenders.

The following table shows the different approaches to Drug Law Enforcement in Manila City.

Table 2
Drug Law Enforcement Approaches

APPROACHES	MEAN	SD
Community Seminars	3.56	0.84
Monitoring Mechanism	2.07	0.92
Stakeholders	3	0
Assistance	1.21	0.51

Table 2 shows the approaches of drug law enforcement to drug offenders concerning the reformation. *Community seminars* topped the approaches with a mean of 3.56 and a standard deviation of 0.84. The second approach used by the law enforcers was *a monitoring mechanism* with a mean of 2.07 and a standard deviation of 0.92, followed by *stakeholders*, mean of 3 and SD of 0, and finally, *assistance* with a mean of 1.21 and SD of 0.51. The monitoring mechanism for dealing with drug offenders included the "Kumustahan Program." The *community stakeholders* played a crucial role in the rehabilitation of offenders.

The data of the researcher got a general response from the respondents from selected police station in Manila, stated that "Dahil sa kakulangan ng programa, talagang depende na sa station chief if may kakilala na kumpanya para bigyan na referral. Madalas ang mga tao sa community ay pinagdududahan na sila agad dahil karamihan ng mga offenders, pag nakulong, nagkaron ng marka o tattoo, sign na galing sila sa loob. Dahil dito, siguro ang tao sa community ay normal na magkaron ng judgment para sa sarili nilang kaligtasan. Hindi natin ito control sa labas. At sa barangay naman, mandato sa kanila na magbigay ng listahan sa mga kanilang nasasakupan na involved sa mga drug related activities. Dahil dito ang mga taga pagpatupad ng batas, ay

nagbabahay bahay upang kumustahin ang mga ito at tingnan ang situwasyon para maverify kong totoo ba o hindi ang nakalista. Pero dahil madalas ang reshuffle system sa Manila, ang mga intel ay hindi gaano natutukan kaya madalas nagkakaron ng pagkaibaiba ng datos”.

The researcher found this particular research question seemingly neglected by the department. Only a few drug officers were aware of the programs stipulated by the justice system and the constitution. This is a big problem for the criminal justice systems because the frequent change of leadership would bring about the interruption, and even worse, discontinued implementation of the programs.

In this particular matter, the researcher believed that the approach of law enforcement was wide problematic due to incompetent leadership and the vested interest of the person in authority in the said agency. It seemed neglected because law enforcement might not know the existing approaches, and the prevailing self-interest mattered. This is what Brown’s (2015) study emphasized about behavioral concerns concerning "bad apples" in the department.

Research Question 3: What is the percentage rate of the drug cases in the city of Manila from 2017 up to 2020?

*Table 3
Manila Anti-Illegal Drug Operations Percentage. 2017-2020*

OPERATION DESCRIPTION		Year			
		2020	2019	2018	2017
Drug Operations Conducted		2056	2262 (+10%)	2365 (+15%)	2673 (+30%)
Case Filed in Court		4964	5560 (+12%)	5362 (+8%)	6106 (+23%)
Arrested	User	2845	3272 (+15%)	3414 (+20%)	3756 (+32%)
	Pusher	1056	1141 (+8%)	1247 (+18%)	1352 (+28%)

Source: DILG & PNP- MPD Annual Report 2017-2020 on March 11, 2021

Table 3 shows the percentage of drug operations in the City of Manila in 2020 and the previous years of 2019, 2018, and 2017. It was noted that there was a high peak of cases of drug offenders during the first three (3) years as compared to the 2020 data, 30% in 2017, went down to half, 15% in 2018, and 5% in 2019. The cases filed in court were highest in 2017 when the war on drugs was launched, and it became 8% in 2018 and 12% in 2019.

The number of drug offenders, either users or pushers, was high in 2017, 32% and 28%, respectively; 20% and 18% respectively in 2018, and 15% and 8% in 2019. It was observable that the number of offenders decreased because of the efforts made by the law enforcers. The year 2017 marked the active implementation of the war on drugs. Reports and surveillance monitoring activities by the PNP and identifying drug

offenders were primarily due to the concerted efforts of barangay leaders. Imprisonment of drug pushers by DILG, PDEA, and PNP were the activities of the law enforcement agencies which could be described as worthy and remarkable.

The results in *Research Question 3* showed that the rate of drug cases in the City of Manila from 2017 to 2020 decreased due to the government's strict implementation of the drug war. Indeed, it is a sad fact that the root cause of this problem is due to their economic status. The leadership of the current administration also removed the scalawags. The agency transformed and committed to the mandate of the administration to fight the war on drugs within a specific period.

The researcher observed the significant relationship of the study to the findings of the study of Nelid (2017) that explored the susceptibility of politics to influence the criminal justice system at every level. However, the study was able to identify the crisis due to the strong influence and other factors in the criminal justice system. The researcher agreed that the manner of law enforcement approach should be revisited most, especially on the chain of custody, where drug law enforcement can manipulate the case and the pieces of evidence.

In this view, the researcher observed that the percentage rate of drug cases in Manila was due to the lack of jobs for the people. From the demographic profile of the offenders in the City of Manila. It was revealed that most of them had unstable financial incomes. Hence, they became vulnerable individuals and easy prey to drugs.

Research Question 4: What is the extent of the agency's implementation of its various programs in dealing with drug offenders?

Any drug offender reformation program significantly impacts the lives and behavior of these offenders. In coordination with the local government, the national government must have a solid political will to implement such programs. The Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of any program must be reviewed and regularly monitored to determine the extent and effectiveness of its implementation.

*Table 4
Reformation Program based on the Drug Offenders in Manila*

REFORMATION PROGRAMS	Livelihood	LGU Support	Social Amelioration Program	Others: Education, Financial Literacy, Free Rehabilitation, etc.
Government Programs	0%	0%	100 %	0%

Table 4 shows that the drug offenders received only the *Social Amelioration Program (SAP)*, as indicated by the 100% mark, compared to the other criteria, such as livelihood, LGU support, education, financial literacy, and others got a 0% rate. Respondents said that they were not given access to these privileges. The researcher was prompted to inquire, but the LGU officer responded, "*may program naman, kaso MADC or Manila Anti-Drug Council started lang last 2020.*" This response showed that the program was neglected and unsupported (data results see Appendix G).

The researcher found out in *Research Question 3* that the program/s of the agency in dealing with the offender process in Manila were partially implemented due to significant factors. Officers depended mainly on the instructions provided by

department heads. It appeared that the primary goal of the justice system, to get these offenders back to society, was far different and remote from current practices. Given a chance, the researcher brought up matters related to the funding system, and the quick answer was – funds were only for operation, and programs were excluded.

In this regard, the PNP and PDEA, in the entirety of its network and the organization of its sub-agencies, created an atmosphere of confusion and sometimes chaos from within and otherwise. The interface and interplay of these two agencies showed unfavorable and unwanted overlapping of functions, duties, and responsibilities, from which each agency had sets of activities that were undefined and needed redefining.

Research Question 5: What are the acceptance traits of stakeholders in the community after drug offenders' reformation?

Community acceptance of drug offenders is vital for these to change their mindset and think positively as much as possible. The researcher asked the drug offenders why they are involved in drugs and how the community accepts them despite their being such.

The table below shows the reasons for drug offenders' involvement in drug-related cases.

*Table 5
Reasons for Involvement in Drug-Related Case*

REASONS	Poverty	Peers	Personal Problem	Set-up	Curiosity	Others	TOTAL:
Drug Involvement (Number)	30	31	17	14	8	0	100
Drug Involvement (Percentage)	30 %	31 %	17 %	14 %	8 %	0%	100%

Source: Data gathered from 100 Identified Drug Offenders in the City of Manila

Table 5 shows the main reason drug offenders got involved in drug-related cases. *Poverty* received a 30% rating from the respondents, close to a 31% rating for *Peers* from the same respondents. *Personal Problems* is one criterion that got a 17% rating, and a 14% rating indicating the *Set-up or Framed* criterion. The criterion, *curiosity*, got the least 8% rating (data results see Appendix G).

From the data gathered by the researcher, respondents answered that “dahil sa kahirapan, at ang mga barkada lamang ang kasama sa araw araw. Napipilitang gumawa ng hindi maganda at pumasok sa ganitong kalakaran. Mabilis ang pera, pero nakasalalay ang buhay. Dahil kailangan ng pera sa pangaraw-araw na gastusin, kaya walang nagagawa kundi pumasok at magpatangay sa trip ng barkada para magkapera.”

As gleaned from the demographic profile, most offenders are generally *male and married*, and their *Economic Status* and survival stage significantly affect their mindset about drugs. The researcher found that the root cause was *Poverty and Peers'* influence. A small percentage of the data included some ‘personalities offender’s in the society who were given privileges and exceptional treatment as compared to ‘non-personalities offenders’ in the society that were treated far differently. Adding to the problem was that authorities could manipulate the case, and consequently, in the court, the prosecution failed to substantiate the case. This tended to make the offenders suffer emotionally, whether guilty or not, to the commission of a crime, and more so, the offenders' families suffered judgment from the community.

The researcher saw a significant relationship between the findings of the study of Gana (2015), which highlighted the problems faced by the prosecutorial arm of the government in case building. The burden of ensuring guilt and the discrepancies in presenting evidence during trial becomes challenging as seeing the diverse fickle that must be considered. Specifically, under the probable cause practices, the community pre-judges the moral certainty if law enforcement fails to present evidence beyond a reasonable doubt.

The table below shows the Multi-Stakeholders Acceptance Support.

*Table 5.1
Multi-Stakeholders' Acceptance Support*

SUPPORT	Brgy Program/s	Police Referral	Brgy Leaders Referral	Community Leaders' Job Recommendation/s	None at all	TOTAL
Community Acceptance (Number)	33	4	1	0	62	100
Community Acceptance (Percentage)	33 %	4 %	1 %	0 %	62 %	100%

Source: Data gathered from 100 Identified Drug Offenders in the City of Manila

Table 5.1 shows that the average acceptance of multi-stakeholders in the community to drug offenders thru barangay program inclusion got a 33% mark. As to support from law enforcement, offenders who were referred to work depending on skills and qualifications got 4%. Only 1% of the respondents said that the barangay chairman and officers referred them, and most were pre-judged by the community's stakeholders. 62% of the respondents answered that they were discriminated against.

The researcher attested that most drug offenders, in their homecoming, received unusual, scathing, and harmful commentaries from their respective communities. Such would aggravate their feelings of being unwanted and outcast members of society. The study of Nelid (2017) cited that identifying the high target drug offenders was in crisis due to the city's strong influence and other factors that the criminal system was manipulated by law enforcement. The community pillar collectively imposed limitations on the individual behavior of citizens for the common good of a civilized and democratic society that deterred criminality and criminal behavior. Institutions such as barangays, government agencies, legislative bodies, the academe, and religious and civic organizations, among others, were involved in this pillar. It was important to note that the law enforcement pillar had apprehended Filipinos who committed drug crimes in the Philippines.

In this particular matter, the researcher believed that poverty was the root cause of this comprehensive problem on drugs. Added to this was the variable of acceptance level that these drug offenders felt unacceptable in society.

Chapter 5
SUMMARY OF BASIC FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS
AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter summarizes the essential findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

*Research Problem 1: Condition of the drug offenders
in terms of economic and emotional status.*

The economic and emotional state of the offenders significantly affects their involvement in drug-related activities. It is noted that most offenders come from marginalized sectors that need more government attention. Their condition makes them susceptible to selling illegal drugs to ease their problems. In table 1, chapter 4, the author identified the demographic profile of the respondents wherein, from 100 respondents, 61% were depressed and financially challenged.

*Research Problem 2: Prevailing approaches to the drug law
enforcement in the City of Manila*

Table 2 in Chapter 4 presents drug law enforcement's approach to drug offenders. The "tokhang, community talk and monitoring approach" is one of the approaches for implementing and initial discussion of suspected drug offenders in the community. It was the first intervention to get clearance and other requirements from the local leaders.

Research Problem 3: Percentage rate of the drug cases in the city of Manila from 2017 up to 2020.

The data presented in Table 3 in Chapter 4 shows the percentage of drug operations in the City of Manila. Almost 4964 drug cases were filed in courts in 2020 and the previous year. In 2019, the cases rose to (5560) 12%, in 2018, the cases went down to (1141) 8%, and in 2017, the cases were doubled to (6106) 23%. The peak of cases of drug offenders during the first three (3) years as compared to the 2020 data was documented through the monitoring activities of the PNP, DILG, LGU, and PDEA.

Research Problem 4: The extent of the agency's implementation of its various programs in dealing with drug offenders.

The data presentation of Table 4 in Chapter 4 stated that only the Social Amelioration Program (SAP) was served to them as a government program/s. Still, at least for survival purposes, cash assistance from DSWD-SAP was only implemented during the pandemic crisis. SAP was not part of the reformation program or assistance, but most of them couldn't recall any program that served to help their reformation. The Manila Anti-Drug Council-MADC was established in 2020 only. From this view, the study assumed that the city neglected the duty of the enforcers concerning the service and institutional program. Although, the administration has created an integrated treatment program to affect their rehabilitation programs. These include Therapeutic Community Modality, Restorative Justice Principles and concepts, and Volunteer Probation Aides (VPAs).

In January 2018, the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA), together with the PNP and host LGUs established 'Balay Silangan.' It was a national drug reformation providing services to drug offenders who surrendered to authorities, such as continuing education and health awareness, psychological, spiritual, and physical activities, counseling, moral recovery, values formation, and personal and life skills. It was a temporary refuge to reform drug offenders into self-sufficient and law-abiding members of society. Earlier than the launch of Balay Silangan, Kauswagan was already implementing a youth reformation center for drug offenders where beneficiaries underwent a boot camp for discipline and values formation in 2016.

Research Problem 5: Acceptance traits of stakeholders in the community after drug offenders' reformation.

The discussion and data presented in chapter 4, table 5, indicated the leading and most prominent reason for drug offenders' involvement, as peers on top, most of them were under blue-collar (middle worker/laborer) and no collar (unemployed or jobless). There is a clear correlation between the employment rate and drug issues. Therefore, the government should provide job opportunities to encourage people to abandon illegal drug use. Other reasons can also be attributed to any person's financial status and personal problems. Moreover, the problem of framing those people was very alarming. A total of 14% of the participants answered that they were framed. In many instances, the acceptance level of society depends on the reputation of drug offenders.

Table 5.1 shows that the average acceptance level of the stakeholders through barangay programs and enforcement support is vital for the offenders' reformation.

The referral from the barangay office to get a job was highly considered a guarantee. The study also discovered the alarming average of pre-judged, discriminated, and experienced unusual negative words and comments from the community. However, the drug offenders were generally accepted in society but were not equally treated. They experienced judgments and loss of opportunities and were rejected by their relatives. Somehow, because of these incidents, they were forced to return to their addiction because this was their only coping mechanism not to feel the rejection by their families.

CONCLUSION

The root cause of drug usage points to the person's financial well-being. The structure of the society where they live, values, and personality make them uncertain. The causes of poverty, inequality, and powerlessness are a stark reality, contrary to the government's position of treating the issues as a problem of criminality and lawlessness. The drug problem must be addressed using a holistic and rights-based approach, requiring the mobilization and involvement of all stakeholders.

Drug offenders experience rejection and are pre-judged by families and other people in the City of Manila, so law enforcement should establish a solid tie to the general public. Most especially to the stakeholders to reconcile massive problems of drug cases in the city.

Drug law enforcement programs for drug offenders are neglected. It is a crucial task for all law enforcement agencies, such as PNP and the PDEA. These agencies should firmly commit to the justice system's goals. Drug offenders are being judged negatively and considered outcasts by society. Acceptance traits of the community proved to be generally unfavorable and unrewarding, eliciting from the offenders' feelings of guilt, inferiority, and hopelessness.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the foregoing findings and the conclusions drawn, and within the scope and limitations of the study, the researcher recommends:

1. To improve the general institutional approach. This means there is a need to recalibrate the procedures regarding drug law enforcement. This is crucial to evaluate the strategies and achieve institutional objectives.
2. To encourage data sharing across government agencies. This is to address issues about the percentage of drug-related cases.
3. To re-evaluate policies that will result in the reform of the rehabilitation centers. All forms of government support are needed to achieve the system's institutional goal. The lack of coordination of government agencies hinders the effective delivery of services to the offenders.
4. To increase funds for drug law enforcement operations and rehabilitation centers. It is the Act of the government to initiate and support strong ties with stakeholders within the community.
5. To improve suspects' condition, encourage them to help improve their condition.

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APPENDIX A

PNP - Manila Police District, Permit to Gather Data

Republic of the Philippines
NATIONAL POLICE COMMISSION
PHILIPPINE NATIONAL POLICE, NATIONAL CAPITAL REGION POLICE OFFICE
MANILA POLICE DISTRICT
DISTRICT PERSONNEL AND RECORDS MANAGEMENT DIVISION
United Nations Avenue, Ermita, Manila

MEMORANDUM

TO : C, DDEU and Station Commanders, PS-1 to PS-14

FROM : AC, DPRMD

SUBJECT : **Data Gathering for Research**

DATE : March 11, 2021

1. Reference: Letter request to DD, MPD dated March 5, 2021.

2. This pertains to the request of Mr Bob A Aguilar, a Graduate School researcher from the University of the East-Manila, to conduct interview to anti-illegal drugs operatives of this Police District relative to data gathering for his research entitled "Law Enforcement in the Criminal Justice System, Reformation Approach of the Drug Offenders in Manila City". The following are his statements of the problem:

- a. How law enforcement identifies those drug suspects in the community?
- b. What are the screening processes in verifying suspected offenders?
- c. What are the approaches used by the law enforcement in relation to the drug offenders?
- d. How many drug offenders in Manila from 2017 up to 2020?
- e. How law enforcement helps these drug offenders to their reformation?

3. In this regard, please accommodate the request of Mr Aguilar to gather data for his research by interviewing the following number of anti-illegal drugs operatives in your respective units/police stations relative to his research without causing prejudice to the PNP organization:

- a. Four (4) anti-illegal drugs operatives from DDEU; and
- b. One (1) anti-illegal drugs operative for every police station.

4. For appropriate action.

SAMUEL B PABONITA
Police Lieutenant Colonel

Copy Furnished:
Command Group

APPENDIX B

Questionnaire for the Law Enforcement

“REFORMING THE INSTITUTIONAL APPROACH IN THE DRUG LAW ENFORCEMENT IN MANILA CITY”

for LAW ENFORCEMENT / OFFICERS questionnaire

IMPORTANT REMINDERS: In observance of Republic Act No. 10173, or also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all information will be kept with the utmost confidentiality and would be used for academic purposes only. The names of the respondents will not appear in the thesis publications resulting from this study unless permission makes a guarantee to do so. **(Please check your answer corresponding to the questions below).**

5	Strongly Required
4	Required
3	Consider
2	Less Consider
1	Not Consider

1	Age Range (21-25 y/o)	6	Age Range (46 - 50 y/o)
2	Age Range (26 -30 y/o)	7	Age Range (51 - 55 y/o)
3	Age Range (31 - 35 y/o)	8	Age Range (56 - 60 y/o)
4	Age Range (36 - 40 y/o)	9	Age Range (61 - 65 y/o)
5	Age Range (41 - 45 y/o)	10	Age Range (66 & up y/o)

Full Name (optional): _____ Please encircle the no. of your AGE level: ____
 Current Designation: _____ Under what SG: _____
 Years of service: _____ Field of Study: _____
 Gender: Male Female LGBTQA+ Member (if any, please state): _____

1.)	Law Enforcement following the systematic process in (OPERATIONS / IDENTIFYING) drug offenders in the City of Manila?	5	4	3	2	1
2.)	Level of accuracy that the list of law enforcement in relation to drug offenders?	5	4	3	2	1
3.)	In verifying drug offenders, law enforcement conduct internal investigation?	5	4	3	2	1
4.)	Is the intervention of law enforcement to the drug offenders considered?	5	4	3	2	1
5.)	Law enforcement providing seminars in educating people in the community about drug effects?	5	4	3	2	1
6.)	After the drug offenders' grant liberty, law enforcement considered the mechanism in monitoring the activities of these offenders?	5	4	3	2	1
7.)	Law enforcement value the importance of stakeholders?	5	4	3	2	1
8.)	Law enforcement provide assistance to the drug offenders for the restoration of their lives?	5	4	3	2	1

OPEN ENDED QUESTION/s:

9. What are the prevailing laws considered by the law enforcement in drug operations?
10. How law enforcement act on the list provided? Offenders Classification.
11. After verifying, what is the intervention of law enforcement to the drug offenders?
12. Which agency or department is in-charge with the monitoring and reformation of the offenders?
13. If drug offenders' granted the liberty, is law enforcement has mechanism in monitoring the activities of these offenders?
14. Statistical data of Drug Offenders' in the city of Manila from 2017 – 2020.

No. _____ Participant Signature: _____

Date & Time: _____

APPENDIX C

Questionnaire for the Drug Offenders

“REFORMING THE INSTITUTIONAL APPROACH IN THE DRUG LAW ENFORCEMENT IN MANILA CITY”

for DRUG OFFENDERS' questionnaire

IMPORTANT REMINDERS: In observance to Republic Act No. 10173, or also known as Data Privacy Act of 2012, all information will be kept with utmost confidential and would be used for academic purposes only. The names of the respondents will not appear in the thesis publications resulting from this study unless a permission make guarantee to do so. **(Please answer corresponding questions below).**

Full Name (optional): _____
 Gender: Male Female LGBTQA+ Member (if any, please state): _____
 Marital Status: Single Married Widowed Separated Divorced
 Please encircle the no. of your current JOB classification: _____ Please encircle the no. of your AGE Level: _____

1	White Collar	Working Professionals
2	Blue Collar	Middle Workers / laborer
3	Pink Collar	Less pay than white/blue, healthcare and beauty services
4	Gold Collar	Own flex-time, Employer, Business owners
5	Grey Collar	Multi-talented, retired but still working
6	Orange Collar	Mining and Construction line of work
7	Black Collar	Artists, Producers and others
8	Red Collar	Government Officer and Employee
9	No Collar	Jobless / Unemployed

1	Age Range (17 - below)
2	Age Range (18 - 20 y/o)
3	Age Range (21 - 25 y/o)
4	Age Range (26 - 30 y/o)
5	Age Range (31 - 35 y/o)
6	Age Range (36 - 40 y/o)
7	Age Range (41 - 45 y/o)
8	Age Range (46 - 50 y/o)
9	Age Range (51 - 55 y/o)
10	Age Range (56 - 60 y/o)

if any,
 Number of dependent/s: _____
 Your case description as related to the court CASE FILE: _____

Please CHECK ALL if applicable:

Your reason/s to the involvement of drug related cases?	<input type="checkbox"/> : Poverty	<input type="checkbox"/> : Set-up
	<input type="checkbox"/> : Influenced by peers	<input type="checkbox"/> : Curiosity to use
As drug offenders, (please state if possible) What support/s have you been access in the community?	<input type="checkbox"/> : Personal Problem	<input type="checkbox"/> : Drug Supplier
	<input type="checkbox"/> : Personal Consumption	<input type="checkbox"/> : Drug Carrier
Does reporting method required by the law enforcement?	<input type="checkbox"/> : Livelihood	<input type="checkbox"/> : LGU Program
	<input type="checkbox"/> : Education	<input type="checkbox"/> : Stakeholders Support
What is the method have been recommended or advised by the law enforcement?	<input type="checkbox"/> : Financial Literacy	<input type="checkbox"/> : Free Rehabilitation
	<input type="checkbox"/> : PESO - Work	<input type="checkbox"/> : Others:
	<input type="checkbox"/> : YES	If yes, <input type="checkbox"/> : Weekly
	<input type="checkbox"/> : NO	<input type="checkbox"/> : Monthly
		<input type="checkbox"/> : Quarterly
		<input type="checkbox"/> : Annually

What is the method have been recommended or advised by the law enforcement?

<input type="checkbox"/> : Personal appearance in the nearest Police Station	<input type="checkbox"/> : Account Online Portal as provided by the agency
<input type="checkbox"/> : Personal appearance in the nearest DILG Office	<input type="checkbox"/> : By local barangay reporting
<input type="checkbox"/> : Personal appearance in the nearest City Hall	<input type="checkbox"/> : By representative reporting to any concern agencies

No. _____ Participant Signature: _____ Date & Time: _____

APPENDIX D

Law Enforcement Data Results Summary

Quantitative

Respondents:	Age	FOS	Gender	RQ 1	RQ 2	RQ 3	RQ 4	RQ 5	RQ 6	RQ 7	RQ 8
1	2	1	1	4	4	5	3	5	1	3	1
2	2	1	1	4	4	5	4	5	1	3	1
3	2	1	1	4	4	5	4	3	1	3	1
4	2	1	1	4	4	5	4	5	1	3	1
5	2	1	1	4	4	5	4	3	1	3	1
6	2	1	1	4	4	5	4	5	1	3	1
7	4	1	1	4	4	5	4	3	1	3	3
8	4	1	1	4	4	5	4	5	1	3	1
9	4	2	1	4	4	5	4	5	1	3	1
10	4	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	1
11	4	1	1	5	5	5	3	3	3	3	3
12	6	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
13	6	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
14	6	1	1	5	5	5	3	3	1	3	3
15	6	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	3
16	4	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	1
17	4	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	3
18	4	1	1	5	5	5	4	5	1	3	2
19	4	1	1	4	4	5	4	5	1	3	2
20	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	5	1	3	2
21	3	1	1	5	5	5	3	5	1	3	2
22	3	1	1	4	4	5	4	5	3	3	1
23	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	5	3	3	1
24	5	1	1	5	5	5	4	5	3	3	1
25	2	1	1	5	5	5	3	3	3	3	2
26	2	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
27	2	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
28	5	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	2
29	5	1	1	4	4	5	4	3	3	3	2
30	5	1	1	5	5	5	4	5	3	3	2
31	2	1	1	4	4	5	4	5	3	3	2
32	2	1	1	5	5	5	4	5	1	3	2
33	2	1	1	5	5	5	4	5	1	3	2
34	4	1	1	5	5	5	3	5	1	3	1
35	2	2	1	5	5	5	4	5	1	3	1

36	4	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	1	3	1
37	4	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	1	3	1
38	3	2	2	5	5	5	4	5	1	3	1
39	3	1	2	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	1
40	3	1	2	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	1
41	3	1	2	4	4	5	3	3	1	3	1
42	3	1	2	5	5	5	3	5	1	3	1
43	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
44	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
45	3	1	2	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
46	3	1	2	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
47	3	1	2	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	1
48	2	1	2	4	4	5	3	3	1	3	1
49	4	1	1	5	5	5	3	3	1	3	1
50	2	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	1
51	2	2	1	5	5	5	3	3	1	3	1
52	4	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	1
53	4	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	1
54	4	2	2	4	4	5	4	3	1	3	1
55	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	1
56	3	2	2	5	5	5	4	3	1	3	1
57	3	2	2	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
58	3	1	2	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
59	3	2	2	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
60	3	1	1	4	4	5	3	3	3	3	1
61	3	1	1	4	4	5	4	3	3	3	1
62	3	1	1	4	4	5	3	3	3	3	1
63	3	1	1	4	4	5	4	3	3	3	1
64	3	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
65	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
66	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
67	3	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
68	3	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
69	3	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
70	3	2	1	5	5	5	3	4	3	3	1
71	3	2	1	5	5	5	3	4	3	3	1
72	4	2	1	5	5	5	4	4	3	3	1
73	4	2	1	4	4	5	4	4	3	3	1
74	4	2	1	4	4	5	4	3	3	3	1
75	4	2	1	4	4	5	3	3	3	3	1
76	3	1	1	5	5	5	3	3	3	3	1
77	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	2	3	1
78	3	1	1	5	5	5	3	3	2	3	1

79	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
80	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
81	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
82	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	2	3	1
83	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	2	3	1
84	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
85	3	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	2	3	1
86	3	2	1	5	5	5	4	4	2	3	1
87	3	2	1	5	5	5	4	4	2	3	1
88	3	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	2	3	1
89	3	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
90	4	2	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
91	4	2	1	5	5	5	4	4	2	3	1
92	4	2	1	5	5	5	4	4	2	3	1
93	5	2	1	5	5	5	4	4	2	3	1
94	5	1	1	5	5	5	4	4	2	3	1
95	5	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	2	3	1
96	5	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	2	3	1
97	5	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	2	3	1
98	5	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1
99	5	1	1	4	4	5	4	3	3	3	1
100	5	1	1	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1

APPENDIX E

Drug Offenders Data Results

<p>Research Problem 4: What are the acceptance traits of stakeholders in the community after a drug offender's reformation?</p> <p>To assess the factors that may affect the acceptance traits of the stakeholders in the community. <i>The researcher asked</i> the respondents about their case details, what provisions of the law they violated, and the top two (2), most reasons are the following are:</p>	
<p>Under R.A. 9165, Sec 5, offenders are arrested for drug trade and selling drugs. Respondents admitted that selling drugs helps them to survive in their daily lives. The needs of their family are the most important, which is why they sell drugs on the streets for easy money.</p>	Less Dominant
<p>Under R.A. 9165, Sec 11, for offenders arrested for the possession of drugs, respondents admitted that they are using drugs to ease the pain, problem, and other conflicts that they encountered in their lives.</p>	Most Violations that the respondents committed
<p>The respondents were also asked about their reasons for involvement, and the following top five (5) reasons are:</p>	
<p>1. Peers influence due to "samahan" and "barkadahan" system, most respondents answered that they committed the crimes because of the influence of their respective friends and people around them.</p>	31% - Extreme Reason
<p>2. Poverty problem, offenders take risk in order to survive the daily needs of their family. Offenders choose to sell drugs because of easy money in the streets. As stated "<i>Sa hirap ng buhay, walang trabaho, kumakalam sa sikmura, kaya napilitang pumasok sa ganitong hanap buhay</i>".</p>	30%
<p>3. Personal Problem that lead to some of the offenders use drugs as easing and forget temporarily the problem. As respondents stated "<i>Maraming problem sa bahay, magulo ang pamilya, puro away, kaya para makalimot, gumagamit nang kasi masarap sa pakiramdam</i>".</p>	17%
<p>4. Some offenders say they are set up only for the crime because of a personal issue and vested interest. Police planted the evidence, and they cannot do anything about it. They don't have influential family or "kakosa" to back them up. As respondents stated "<i>Hindi naman ganito ang kaso namin, naset-up lang kami ng pulis kasi gusto nila my mahuli, at tinaniman kami ng drugs</i>".</p>	14%
<p>5. Offenders Curiosity, the feeling of, and the experienced of taking drugs. These reasons of curiosity about the minor or person having personal problems attract the offenders. As general answer "<i>Gusto ko lang matikman at malaman ang pakiramdam, para makalimot</i>".</p>	8%

Mixed-Method

Respondents:	Gender	Marital Status	Source of Income	Age	RQ1	RQ2	RQ3	RQ4	RQ5
1	1	4	2	5	3	1	5	3	2
2	1	2	2	3	1	1	4	3	2

3	1	2	2	6	1	1	5	3	2
4	1	2	4	3	1	1	2	3	2
5	1	2	1	3	3	1	5	3	2
6	1	4	9	3	3	1	1	3	2
7	1	4	4	7	2	1	5	3	2
8	1	2	6	5	2	2	2	3	2
9	1	2	9	3	1	2	5	3	2
10	3	1	1	6	1	2	3	3	2
11	1	4	3	6	1	2	2	3	2
12	2	4	2	6	1	2	2	3	2
13	3	1	2	3	1	2	4	3	2
14	3	1	3	5	1	1	5	3	2
15	3	1	9	5	1	1	1	3	2
16	2	2	2	3	3	1	2	3	2
17	2	4	9	7	1	1	2	3	2
18	1	2	8	3	1	1	2	3	2
19	3	1	9	3	1	1	5	3	2
20	3	1	9	4	1	1	2	3	2
21	1	2	8	4	1	1	2	3	2
22	1	2	2	4	1	1	2	3	2
23	3	1	2	4	1	1	2	3	2
24	1	2	8	4	1	1	2	3	2
25	1	2	2	5	1	1	2	3	2
26	3	1	2	4	1	1	2	3	2
27	1	2	2	4	1	1	1	3	2
28	3	1	2	5	1	1	1	3	2
29	3	1	9	4	1	2	5	3	2
30	3	1	2	4	1	2	1	3	2
31	3	1	3	4	1	2	2	3	2
32	3	1	9	4	1	2	4	3	2
33	1	2	9	4	1	2	2	3	2
34	1	2	9	5	1	1	4	3	2
35	1	2	3	5	2	1	2	3	2
36	3	1	9	4	1	1	2	3	2
37	1	2	9	5	1	2	4	3	2
38	1	2	3	4	1	2	1	3	2
39	1	4	3	4	1	2	1	3	2
40	1	4	2	5	1	2	1	3	2
41	1	4	2	6	2	2	1	3	2
42	1	4	2	6	2	2	1	3	2
43	1	4	2	6	1	2	2	3	2
44	1	2	2	4	2	2	1	3	2
45	1	2	2	4	2	2	1	3	2

46	1	2	2	3	1	2	3	3	2
47	1	2	9	3	1	2	3	3	2
48	3	1	9	5	1	2	3	3	2
49	3	1	9	4	1	1	3	3	2
50	1	2	2	4	1	1	3	3	2
51	1	2	2	4	1	1	2	3	2
52	1	1	9	4	3	1	1	3	2
53	1	1	9	4	3	2	1	3	2
54	1	1	9	4	3	2	4	3	2
55	1	1	2	4	1	2	1	3	2
56	2	2	2	4	1	2	1	3	2
57	2	2	4	4	3	2	1	3	2
58	2	4	4	7	3	2	1	3	2
59	2	4	2	4	1	2	4	3	2
60	2	4	2	4	1	2	2	3	2
61	2	2	2	5	1	2	1	3	2
62	2	2	2	4	3	2	4	3	2
63	2	2	2	4	1	2	1	3	2
64	2	2	4	7	3	2	2	3	2
65	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	3	2
66	2	2	2	3	1	2	4	3	2
67	2	2	4	3	3	2	4	3	2
68	2	4	9	5	1	2	1	3	2
69	1	4	9	6	1	2	3	3	2
70	1	2	9	6	1	1	3	3	2
71	1	4	9	4	2	1	3	3	2
72	1	4	9	3	2	1	3	3	2
73	1	4	2	3	1	1	3	3	2
74	1	4	2	3	1	2	3	3	2
75	1	2	4	4	1	2	3	3	2
76	1	4	2	4	1	2	2	3	2
77	1	2	2	4	2	2	2	3	2
78	1	2	2	7	2	2	2	3	2
79	1	2	2	4	2	2	4	3	2
80	1	1	2	3	1	2	2	3	2
81	1	1	2	3	1	2	2	3	2
82	1	1	2	3	1	2	4	3	2
83	1	1	2	3	1	2	2	3	2
84	1	2	2	3	2	2	2	3	2
85	1	2	2	7	2	2	2	3	2
86	1	2	9	4	2	2	4	3	2
87	1	2	9	4	2	1	4	3	2
88	2	1	9	3	1	2	1	3	2
89	2	1	9	3	1	2	1	3	2

90	2	1	9	4	1	2	3	3	2
91	2	1	9	4	1	2	1	3	2
92	1	2	9	7	2	2	1	3	2
93	1	2	9	4	2	2	3	3	2
94	1	1	9	3	1	2	1	3	2
95	2	1	9	3	1	2	1	3	2
96	1	1	9	3	1	2	1	3	2
97	1	2	9	7	2	2	1	3	2
98	2	1	4	4	1	2	3	3	2
99	1	2	4	3	2	2	1	3	2
100	2	1	9	4	1	2	3	3	2

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EMPLOYMENT STATUS

- 2020 – Present : **President and CEO**
Meta Phil-Tech Corporation
Office of Manila and Rizal
- 2019 – Present : **Head of Business Operational Permit Adviser**
Philippine Business Permit Assistance
National (Luzon, Visayas and Mindanao)
- 2018 – Present : **SHS Faculty Member, Senior High School Department**
University of Perpetual Help System – Jonelta – PHCM
- 2017 – Present : **CAS Faculty Member, College of Arts and Sciences**
University of Perpetual Help System – Jonelta – PHCM
- 2016 – Present : **President and Head of Executive Consultant**
B.A. Management Consultation Services
Sampaloc, City of Manila
- 2010 – Present : **Freelance** in H.R., Management Policy and Labor Consultant

ACADEMIC DEGREES

- Graduate Degree : **Master in Public Administration**
University of the East – Graduate School, Manila, 2022
- Executive Course : **Professional Education in Special Education**
Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Maynila, 2019
- Risk Management, Professional Certificate**
International Business Management Institute, Berlin Germany, 2014
- Bachelor Degree : **Bachelor of Arts in Political Science**
University of the East, Manila, 2018
- Bachelor of Science in Computer Science**
System Technology Institute, STI Caloocan, 2008